

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes with Catechol and Thiophene-2-carboxylic acid

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The complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} formed with catechol and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid have been studied potentiometrically by the method of Calvin and Bjerrum as modified by Irving and Rossotti, in aqueous media in the presence of 1.0M sodium perchlorate to maintain 0.2M ionic strength. The order of stability is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+}$ with catechol and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid at 50°, 40° and 30° respectively which is in accordance with Irving-William rule. The values of overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have also been evaluated at 40° by carrying out the experiments at 30°, 40° and 50°. The absorption spectra of the complexes favours distorted octahedral stereochemistry around metal ion in solution.

THIOPHENE-2-carboxylic acid and especially catechol are known to be efficient complexing agents. Their complexes with different metal ions have been reported in literature. The complexes of catechol with copper(II) has been studied both by potentiometric and polarographic methods¹⁻⁵. Athavale and his coworkers⁶ have studied the copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of catechol using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique. Lumme and his coworkers⁷ have determined the stability constants of thiophene-2-carboxylic acid complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} in aqueous sodium perchlorate solution at ionic strength 0.986 and reported the values to be $10^{1.54}$, $10^{1.68}$ and $10^{2.02}$ respectively. In this communication stability constants at ionic strength 0.2M and thermodynamic functions of the complexes of catechol and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} are being reported.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B. D. H. AnalaR quality. In order to avoid the complexing tendencies of the anions, metal perchlorates were prepared by refluxing the respective metal carbonates with perchlorate acid till an excess of carbonate was left. The filtrate was neutral solution of metal perchlorate. However, a slightly different method was followed for the preparation of copper perchlorate solution⁸. The amounts of metals present were estimated with EDTA solution. By proper dilution, 0.01M metal perchlorate solutions were prepared from the above estimated stock solutions. Since both catechol and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid are soluble in water, their standard solutions were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity in conductivity water. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by the method of Allen and Low⁹. Its 0.2M solution was prepared by standardisation with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution. Perchloric acid (0.1M) solution was prepared by diluting 60 percent perchloric acid and standardised with standard sodium hydroxide solution. Nitrogen gas free from CO_2 and moisture was bubbled to keep the inert atmosphere and to stir the solution.

For each set of experiments, three titrations were carried out by Calvin-Bjerrum¹⁰ pH titration technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti¹¹.

a. *Acid titration.* Perchloric acid (0.1M, 5.00 ml) + sodium perchlorate (1.0M, 9.50 ml) + conductivity water (35.50 ml).

b. *Reagent titration.* Perchloric acid (0.1M, 5.00 ml) + sodium perchlorate (1.0M, 9.00 ml) + reagent (0.05M, 10.00 ml) + conductivity water (26.00 ml).

c. *Metal titration.* Perchloric acid (0.1M, 5.00 ml) + sodium perchlorate (1.0M, 8.95 ml) + reagent (0.05M, 10.00 ml) + metal solution (0.01M, 5.00 ml) + conductivity water (21.05 ml). An appropriate quantity of sodium perchlorate (1.00M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength, $\mu = 0.2M$. The initial volume of the solution was 50 ml in each case. The plots of pH of the solutions against the volume of the alkali added were drawn. The shapes of the titration curves were as usual.

Apparatus. pH measurements were made using a Philips pH meter model PR 9405M/90 with glass and calomel electrodes assembly and Digicord pH meter model M120 with single electrode assembly. The thermostated bath temperatures were maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $50 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants. The proton-ligand formation curve was obtained by plotting the degree of formation (\bar{n}_H) of the proton-ligand complex against pH using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti¹¹.

The proton-ligand stability constants of the two ligands have been obtained as Bjerrum half-integral value. The same have also been calculated by point-wise calculation method at different points using following two equations

$$\log K_1^H = pH + \log \bar{n}_H / (1 - \bar{n}_H)$$

$$\log K_2^H = pH + \log (\bar{n}_H - 1) / (2 - \bar{n}_H)$$

In case of catechol since the values of \bar{n}_H do not go below one even at high pH, the value of $\log K_1^H$ has therefore been verified by using the following relationship

$$\log K_1^H K_2^H = 2 pH \text{ (at } \bar{n}_H = 1)$$

The complex-ligand formation curve was then obtained by plotting degree of formation of complex (\bar{n}) against the negative logarithm of the concentration of non-protonated ligand (pL) using the relationships derived by Irving and Rossotti¹¹.

For the determination of metal-ligand stability constants, Bjerrum half-integral method¹⁰ was used. In addition $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were obtained by point-wise calculation method using the following equations

$$\log K_1 = pL - \log(1 - \bar{n})/\bar{n}$$

$$\log K_2 = pL - \log(2 - \bar{n})/(\bar{n} - 1)$$

Thermodynamic parameters. The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°), accompanying complexation have been determined using the temperature co-efficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation¹².

The value of ΔG° was obtained from the expression, $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln \beta$.

ΔH° was determined with the help of an isobar equation :

$$\frac{d \ln \beta}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT^2}$$

which may be rewritten as

$$\frac{d(\log \beta)}{d(1/T)} = \frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{4.576}$$

The values of $\log \beta$ obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $1/T$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 40° was determined and equated to $-\Delta H^\circ/4.576$. The value of ΔH° was thus obtained. ΔS° was then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T}$$

Results and Discussion

In case of catechol complexes \bar{n} approaches a value of 2, indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes, whereas for thiophene-2-carboxylic acid \bar{n} values remain less than 1 showing the formation of 1:1 complexes only. This is due to the fact that stability of catechol complexes is enhanced with respect to those of thiophene-2-carboxylic acid due to the formation of a five membered ring by the former. Even the stoichiometry of the complexes of these two ligands is governed by the same factor.

The mean values of protonation constants, $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$, stepwise and overall stability constants and the values of thermodynamic parameters for catechol and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE-1. PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS. STEPWISE AND OVERALL METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT THREE TEMPERATURES.

Metal ion	Ligand	Protonation constants/stability constants	Temperature			$-\Delta G^\circ$ (KJ/mole)			ΔH° (KJ/mole) at 40°	ΔS° (J/mole degree) at 40°	
			30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°			
	Catechol	$\log K_1^H$	10.20	9.80	9.75						
		$\log K_2^H$	8.90	8.80	8.75						
		$\log \beta^H$	19.10	18.60	18.50						
		$\log K_1^H$	2.95	3.35	3.65						
	Thiophene-2-carboxylic acid	$\log \beta^H$	2.95	3.35	3.65						
		$\log K_1^H$	2.95	3.35	3.65						
		$\log K_1$	10.96	10.13	10.09	ΔG_1°	63.51	60.64	62.34		
		$\log K_2$	8.09	7.34	7.29	ΔG_2°	46.88	43.94	45.04	-218.59	-364.24
Ni^{2+}	,,	$\log \beta$	19.05	17.47	17.38	ΔG°	110.39	104.58	107.38		
		$\log K_1$	5.47	5.57	5.65	ΔG_1°	31.70	33.34	34.90		
		$\log K_2$	3.09	3.70	3.89	ΔG_2°	17.91	22.15	23.48	+81.96	+439.13
		$\log \beta$	8.56	9.27	9.45	ΔG°	49.61	55.49	58.38		
Co^{2+}	,,	$\log K_1$	5.90	5.25	4.75	ΔG_1°	34.19	31.43	29.34		
		$\log K_2$	3.77	3.56	3.02	ΔG_2°	21.85	21.31	18.66	-177.60	-398.91
		$\log \beta$	9.67	8.81	7.77	ΔG°	56.04	52.74	48.00		
		$\log K_1$	2.15	2.17	2.20	ΔG_1°	12.46	12.99	13.59	+10.01	+73.48
Ni^{2+}	,,	$\log K_1$	2.10	2.16	2.26	ΔG_1°	12.17	12.93	13.96	+9.10	+70.38
		$\log K_1$	2.05	2.17	2.25	ΔG_1°	11.88	12.99	13.90	+15.48	+90.95

TABLE 2—STABILITY OF METAL-CATECHOL COMPLEXES AT 40°

Metal ion	At No.	2nd I. P.	Electronegativity	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
Cu ²⁺	29	20.34	1.75	10.13	7.34	17.47
Ni ²⁺	28	18.20	1.75	5.57	3.70	9.27
Co ²⁺	27	17.31	1.70	5.25	3.56	8.81

The values of log K₁ and log K₂ are positive in all cases. The log K₁ values for catechol complexes are almost five times of those with thiophene-2-carboxylic acid at the same temperature. Perhaps it is due to the difference in pH at which complex formation takes place, as well as the ring size of the complexes. The low value of log K₁ (2.15) in case of copper(II) thiophene-2-carboxylic acid complex is comparable to that of copper-acetic acid complex¹³(1.74), which indicates that sulphur may not be taking part in coordination with the metal ion. A slightly higher value in case of copper(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylic acid complex as compared to copper(II)-acetic acid complex is due to the presence of an aromatic ring in the former. However, in the 50% aqueous-dioxane the log K₁ value 2.91 at 25° at 0.1M ionic strength for copper(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylic acid complex is slightly higher due to the difference of medium, ionic strength and Cu-S interaction as confirmed by N.M.R. study¹⁴.

In case of catechol complexes except for Ni²⁺, log β values at 30° are greater than those at 40° and 50°, indicating that low temperature is favourable for the formation of Cu²⁺ complexes. However, higher temperature is favourable for Ni(II)-catechol complex. The order of stability with catechol at 40° and 50° is Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ which is in accordance with Irving-William rule¹⁵ (Table 1). A relation between log K_n and second ionisation-potential is noted in the present case. This potential indicates that d-orbitals are involved in complex formation as shown by Irving and William (Table 2). However, at 30° with catechol, the order of stability is Cu²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Ni²⁺. This order follows neither the Irving-William rule nor any of the empirical orders reviewed by them. The complete disagreement may be attributed to stabilization by Jahn-Teller distortion for Co²⁺ complexes analogous to that of Cu²⁺ complexes. ΔG° values of Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ complexes with catechol have more negative values at 30° than at 40° and 50°. It is further observed that ΔH° is negative in case of Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ complexes with catechol showing that reaction is exothermic, whereas for Ni²⁺, ΔH° is positive showing that reaction is endothermic. In case of Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ complexes ΔS° is negative showing that entropy term is not favourable for their formation (Table 1).

In case of thiophene-2-carboxylic acid higher temperature is favourable for the formation of complexes since log K₁ values at 50° are greater than at 40° and 30°. At 30° the order of stability is Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ which is in accordance with Irving-William rule. A relation between log K₁ and second I. P. is also noted in this case. ΔG° values of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ complexes with thiophene-2-carboxylic acid are more

negative with increase of temperature. ΔH° is positive in all cases with thiophene-2-carboxylic acid. ΔS° is positive in all cases, hence entropy is favourable for the formation of complexes (Table 1).

The absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded to ascertain the stereochemistry around metal ion. In octahedral cation [Co(H₂O)₆]²⁺, the absorption bands at 8000, 16000 and 19400 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to electronic transition

respectively. The bands at 15600 and 20,000 cm⁻¹ have been observed in the absorption spectra of a complex of cobalt(II) perchlorate with catechol. The position of bands favours distorted octahedral stereochemistry and these bands may be assigned to electronic transition ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ respectively¹⁶. The electronic transition around 8000 cm⁻¹ could not be observed due to absorption of the solvent below 8000 cm⁻¹. The octahedral nickel(II) complexes exhibit a simple spectrum involving three spin allowed transitions which usually occur in the range 7000-13000, 11000-20000 and 19000-27000 cm⁻¹, with low intensities. Sometimes two spin forbidden transitions to 1E_g and ${}^1T_{2g}$ are also observed. In the absorption spectra of [Ni(H₂O)₆]²⁺ three bands at 8000, 13500 and 22500 cm⁻¹ have been observed¹⁷. The absorption spectra of a complex of nickel(II) perchlorate with catechol show bands at 8800, 13500, 15100 and 21500 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to electronic transitions ${}^3T_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, ${}^3T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, ${}^1E_g \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ respectively. This favours distorted octahedral stereochemistry around nickel ion^{16,17}. A broad absorption band around 11,800 cm⁻¹ observed in the complex of copper(II) perchlorate with catechol may be assigned to electronic transition ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ in the distorted octahedral stereochemistry¹⁷.

In general there was no significant shift of major absorption bands of complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with catechol when the temperature of the solution was raised from 30° to 40° or 50° indicating, thereby, that stereochemistry around metal ion practically remains the same at different temperatures. Thus the variation in the stability constant is not due to any stereochemical changes.

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